

Public Spaces by Burle Marx

No other landscape architect has been the protagonist of such significant experimentation in the creation of parks, squares and public gardens in Brazil as Roberto Burle Marx (1909-94). One only has to remember that it was Burle Marx who planned the Parque do Flamengo, in Rio de Janeiro, one of the most important – if not the most important – urban green area planned and executed in Latin America in the second half of the twentieth century. It was Burle Marx who renewed these structures in Brazil's cities, giving them a modern content that distanced them from the tradition that had gradually been consolidated in Brazil since the second half of the 19th century.

After 1850, the reflections of social and economic stability began to be felt in the transformation of the features of some of the country's principal cities, beginning with the imperial capital. Rio de Janeiro came to benefit from a progressive transfer of capital accumulated with the slave trade to real estate business and urban infrastructure, on a previously unseen scale. The city experienced euphoria with all the new works and urban improvements, with sumptuous public buildings, broader streets and avenues and cobblestone paving (1853), gas lighting (1854), a sewage disposal system (1862) and many other novelties.

The second half of the 19th century was also the time when the creation of public and private parks gathered momentum in major Brazilian cities. Changes in the urban standards and lifestyles of the upper and middle classes led to the appreciation of garden spaces in the domestic environment, presenting opportunities for the use of ornamental plants on an unprecedented scale in the country. Remodeling projects and the construction of new avenues and public spaces came to use vegetation as their principal constituent element, to an extent never seen

before. Nevertheless, the choice of botanical specimens was as a rule based on that love of the foreign characterizing so many other activities of the time: preference was given to a limited selection of species imported from Europe, rather than to endemic plants.

It was left to Auguste François Marie Glaziou (1833-1906) to attempt to minimally reverse this situation. A French botanist, landscape architect and hydraulic engineer who had worked with Jean Charles Adolphe Alphand (1817-91) in designing the Bois de Boulogne and Buttes-Chaumont, Glaziou was head of the department of parks and gardens of the Brazilian Imperial House from 1869 to 1897, taking charge of the remodeling and creation of parks and squares, especially in the city of Rio de Janeiro. The renovation of the Campo de Santana (today's Praça da República) and the gardens of the imperial palace of Quinta da Boa Vista were some of his most important works, based on a re-interpretation of the English landscape garden of the 18th century and pioneering landscaping experiments with Brazilian plants. Nevertheless, between giving preference to the use of native species, according to romantic notions, and creating a model genuinely suited to the Brazilian reality, there was still a large gap to be filled.

Facilitating a positive perception of Brazilian nature, unveiling its unique qualities as a point of departure for the preparation of a national culture, was a challenge that gained force among a progressive intellectual circle in Brazil, beginning in the 1920s: a challenge that was shared to a greater or lesser degree by writers, artists and architects seeking the consolidation of modernity in Brazil, working together in the same ideal for a broad socio-economic renewal hitherto unknown in the country. In the arts, in literature and in landscape architecture, the recognition and interpretation of Brazilian flora without the distancing and idealism of the romantics delineated not only esthetic paths in a negation of academic thought. Above all, they expressed the desire to neutralize the backward attitudes and behaviors of the time, synthesized in the mentality of seeing oneself as a foreigner in one's own country, and replacing them through the construction of a culture identified with national values and realities.

Projects in Recife

In landscape architecture, the consolidation and expansion of this effort at renewal occurred with the appearance of the young Burle Marx who in mid-1934 was chosen to head the department of parks and public gardens in Recife, capital of Pernambuco State in the country's Northeast region. In summarizing the implications of this position, suffice it to

say that it was the first concrete opportunity of bringing modern landscape architecture to public works in Brazil, until then restricted to private patronage.

Burle Marx launched a program to rethink public spaces in Recife, combining remodeling several of the principal existing areas of collective leisure, such as the Praça da República, and the creation of new structures, such as the Jardim da Casa Forte, for a total of 15 interventions in different areas of the city.

In this series of projects, Burle Marx initiated a reflection on the modern content that green spaces would take into account, emphasizing four main aspects: the recreational, the artistic, the educational and the environmental. He foresaw the growing importance that squares, gardens and parks would have in a future city transformed principally by the rise in the height of buildings to accommodate an ever growing number of people, by the reduction in private leisure areas and by the harmful effects of industrialization on the quality of the environment, and absorbing some influences from the urban visions of Le Corbusier.

Burle Marx had a clear idea of the role of modern landscape architecture and its power of transformation in the generation of better living conditions through public green spaces. In an article published in the Recife newspaper *Diário da Manhã*, dated June 22, 1935, he wrote:

[...]in large cities the modern park represents a veritable collective lung. It is within it that the urban inhabitant comes to breathe a little pure air, tired of the daily struggle in closed-in offices, asphalt streets and factories.

It is within it that children living in high-rise apartments, houses with cramped backyards or in collective housing can find an open space for their games, enjoying pollution-free air. [...]

The role played by trees and park environments in cities is already well known as regards their effect on climatic conditions. [...]

From the educational point of view, the purpose of the modern park is to bring a little love of nature, supplying us with the means to distinguish our own flora from the exotic [...]

Casa Forte garden

Among the most representative of the projects was the Casa Forte Garden. This was one of the first pragmatic and programmed alternatives to the excesses of the eclectic public garden, without completely breaking away from the academic principles of symmetry, or from compositional axes and from the axial prospects, although giving up the use of *parterres* and topiaries.

In the same article published in the *Diário da Manhã*, of June 22, 1935, Burle Marx gave the local commu-

nity a detailed explanation of his plans for Casa Forte:

The garden will be composed of three lakes, obeying geometric forms of the greatest simplicity. Each one of these, as an educational function, will represent a group of aquatic flora isolated by the geographical origin of their elements, subordinate to the idea of the whole.

The central circular lake will have aquatic flora from the Amazon. In the center of this lake, a statue by Celso Antonio is to be placed, portraying an Indian woman bathing. Surrounding the lake will be a row of mulatto calycophyllum trees, an interesting tree due to its column-like trunk and symmetrical crowns, of great effect in landscaped gardens. Alongside the entrances to the promenade surrounding the lake will be beds of caladia, adding color to the locale. In the four angles will be groups of palms from the Amazon, such as: scheellias, assais, mumbacas, bacabas, urucuris, jouaris etc.

Regarding the two rectangular lakes, one will be dedicated to American flora, the other to exotics. In the former will be found all the variety of the aquatic plants found in our rivers and riverbanks. Around the lake will be bordering plants such as philidendra of the Araceae family, the well-known caladia from the Amazon, with its many-colored leaves; several examples of grasses etc., giving an appearance of tropical exuberance. Walking from the inside to the outside, we will find a lawn and a promenade. And lastly, there will be two avenues with trees such as Bignonia, coral trees, silk-cotton trees etc.

The exotic lake will contain the aquatic flora of the tropical regions of the other continents, such as the lotus, an aquatic plant from the Nile, widely cultivated in India, as well as *Cyperus papyrus*, another Egyptian genus. Among the lake's border species will be species of great beauty such as *Canna indica*, *Salla aethiopica*, *Crinum powell*, *Strelitzia* and several decorative musaceae. Of the larger zinziberaceae we will plant the *bastã-do-imperador*. And among the trees lining the lake will feature: the *pão-teka*, red and yellow flowering flamboyants, various acacias etc.

Madalena Cactarium

The most controversial project was certainly the Madalena Cactarium (later renamed Praça Euclides da Cunha). Manipulating the accentuated contrasts between light and shade and of scales of plant mass, Burle Marx planted avenues of trees typical of Brazil's Northeast on the perimeter, such as the umbra tree, *joazeiro* (*Zizyphus Joazeiro*) and *paus-d'arco* (*Teconia Heptaphylla*), creating shady areas for rest and permanence, and illuminated the central areas to emphasize several Brazilian genera of cactus and species of euphorbiaceae and bromeliad.

This was a solution that signified not only a cultural act of constructing new values and perceptions concerning elements of the Northeastern landscape, but also and above all an answer suitable to the conditions of the local biota. This scientific dimension in attending to botanical and environmental questions was to soon become one of the trademarks of his work.

In a short article published in the *Diário de Recife* of March 14, 1935, Burle Marx explained the essence of his proposal:

A garden that, in protecting us from the sun, also allows us to see something of the curious flora of the Brazilian Northeast. (...) We have intentionally created a cactarium to bring together in it the greatest number possible of Brazilian genera of the cactus family: *Cereus*, *Melocactus*, *Opuntia*, *Pilocereus*, blocks of stone and plants from the families of the bromeliads and the euphorbiaceae will complete this Northeastern environment.

Pampulha Casino

It was only in the period 1942 to 1945 that circumstances allowed Burle Marx to continue the experimentation begun with public spaces in Recife. The landscape architect was charged with designing a series of parks, squares and gardens in the state of Minas Gerais, among which the surroundings of the Pampulha Casino in the city of Belo Horizonte. The area consisted of a well-defined antechamber with natural elements, which subtly signaled the transition into the interiors of a fine building designed by Oscar Niemeyer. Redefining the topographical virtues of the locale – an elevated peninsula –, Burle Marx marked strategic areas of the lawns with predominantly herbaceous and shrub species and just one group of palms, drawing lines and visual force fields that led the eyes toward the building.

With qualities imperceptible at a distance, it was the frontal area ordering the accesses to the architecture that was the principal environment of the landscape solution. Its lively grounds contained a small central depression with a lake for the cultivation of aquatic species and of moist soil. This was a space structured according to more elaborate associations of colors than those in the surrounding area, achieving dynamism with the seasonal characteristics of the vegetation.

Parque do Barreiro

Following the Casino gardens, Burle Marx embarked on a seminal experience for the times: the planning of the Parque do Barreiro, next to the Grande Hotel and Spa, located around eight kilometers from the city of Araxá in the state of Minas Gerais. The complex was an ambitious landscap-

ing and architectural project of state governor Benedito Valadares, and it soon figured among the biggest government-financed undertakings in Brazil in the forties.

In July 1943, when Burle Marx began designing the landscape project in partnership with botanist Henrique L. de Mello Barreto, the hotel was almost completed and consisted of no less than 320 apartments, with all the infrastructure needed to provide maximum comfort for 600 guests. These included special recreational salons for smoking, a casino, restaurant, cinema-theater etc. The spa too was almost finished, with its 120 bathing rooms and partitioned areas for various types of medicinal treatment.

Burle Marx's access to Valadares led to other work fronts: the Andrade Júnior pavilion with its alkaline sulfur springs and a new architecture project for the sports complex. Burle Marx handed over these projects to Francisco Bolonha (born in 1923), who was an apprentice training in Marx's office at the time. The solution adopted by Bolonha for the thermal spring pavilion was based on a daring curved roof, launched in complete plastic harmony with the landscaping of Burle Marx, in a convergence that had not been possible to establish with the two principal buildings planned in Mission style by Luiz Signorelli.

The Parque do Barreiro was the first project in which Burle Marx studied on a large scale the curves in the compositional organization of the landscaped whole, breaking with the previous syntax of the Pernambuco phase and the revisiting of academic principles, in favor of modern plastic concepts, such as asymmetry. It was a project that mainly signaled the introduction of a new focus in his work, which would strengthen over the following years. And this was the ecological interest in flora and the natural environment, with increased appreciation of the potential use in landscaping of plant associations already existing in nature itself. Making gardens, designing parks, constructing landscapes became not only an esthetic-cultural project, but also one that was scientific.

A pioneering project in Brazil, the park comprised 25 environments that sought to creatively reinvent the natural landscapes of Minas Gerais, emphasizing the wide variety of species occurring in the state's flora. The project's presentation drew attention to the fact that this unheard-of solution was not only an objective and suitable alternative, but also represented a critical view of "the monotony which as a rule one sees in the majority of other [parks] in Brazil, derived from the use of a restricted number of elements, mostly exotic species, continually repeated until resulting in a uniform appearance."

The main avenue of access to the hotel and the spa would be formed of rows of wild pines of the

Podocarpus genus. Close to the right flank of the spa there was to be a palm grove with buritys, bambassus, inadiás, macaúbas, guarirobas, jerivás, caudron palms, tucumas, among others, followed by a section associated with extremely dry climates (xerophiles). There would be a cactarium and plants typical of the state's *caatinga* (dry scrub) vegetation, such as barrigudas, embiruçus, jaracatiás and spurge nettles. And following this, a group characteristic of the iron-ore bearing clay soils of the Serra do Curral mountain range, with tree lilies, arnica, orchids, bromeliads and various other plants.

One then crossed an area of semi-xerophyte species, which extended to the bridge to the Ilha dos Amores Island, composed of species of *tabebuia* (ipê), cassias and other dense, leafy plants. In the following stretch, on the higher slopes of the elevation leading to the perimeter avenue, were to be denser woods with various species of Brazilian spider flower. Almost at the sports complex were to be planted hot climate, thorny species from the limestone formation of Bambuí. The side of the hotel facing the lake would have gardens of araceae and rocks. At the front face would be plants from the Itacolomi series. In this same area, near the canal draining the acidic waters, there would be resistant lavoisieras, microlícias, trembleyas, among others; and in the drier parts, quartzite vegetation.

The official inauguration of the complex took place on April 19, 1944, although the work on the gardens was not totally concluded. The work continued though mid-August of that year, when it was stopped despite appeals to the governor by Burle Marx. Of the 25 sectors originally planned, seven were never realized.

Praça Santa Rosa and Parque Vereda

With the frustrating interruption of work at the Parque do Barreiro, Burle Marx turned his attentions back to Pampulha in Belo Horizonte, aiming to get further state government projects in the residential neighborhood, where he had already worked two years before. Between 1944 and 1945, he managed to convince the mayor, Juscelino Kubitschek, who would later become president of Brazil and initiate the construction of Brasília, to equip the region with a further series of public areas for recreation and leisure. In this series of projects, there were two that took up and continued the studies at Araxá. These were the Praça Santa Rosa and the Parque Vereda.

The Praça Santa Rosa was based on the use of a vast range of xerophyllite plants (191), that is, adapted to stony desert environments, brought together in three large groups – one following ecological criteria and the others according to geological and phyto-geological characteristics.

The Vereda Park consisted of a systemic approach to the role of water, riverbanks and the relationship between flora and fauna in the creation of public green spaces for recreation. This was at a time when the presence of open rivers or badly drained or filled wetlands was synonymous with unsanitary conditions and backwardness in the country's urban environment.

These were proposals that sought not only an immediate answer suited to the conditions of the land in which they would be implemented, or even the use of pre-existing plant formations, but also signaled the consolidation of an ecological and conservationist approach completely unheard of in terms of landscaping in the Brazil of the forties. This was at a time when there was virtually no social awareness over the need for rational management and preservation of the natural heritage. Nevertheless, the innovative nature of the two proposals ended up not seeing the light of day.

Praça Salgado Filho

Two years after the proposals for the Praça Santa Rosa and the Vereda Park, in 1947, Burle Marx began the planning of his first public park in Rio de Janeiro: the Praça Salgado Filho. This consisted of a green reception area for travelers landing at the city's Santos Dumont airport.

The landscaping proposal was based on the idea of producing a beautiful showcase of tropical Brazilian vegetation, offering the visitor principally native species seldom seen in the country's public spaces, nor even in urban landscaping projects. The space was organized taking as its center point a lake for aquatic species, exploring accentuated formal chromatic contrasts and textures between the groups of trees and palms, asymmetrical balances of scale of the vegetation groups and contrasting arrangements between the areas paved with Portuguese mosaics, lawns, flower beds and groups of rocks.

Undertaking this showcase for the city was a task with several specific conditions. The ground for the project was reclaimed landfill, with sandy or rocky soil. Jutting into the sea, the area was at times swept by strong winds and the soil highly saline.

These conditions gave Burle Marx the idea of using a selection of resistant and already adapted vegetation, such as several species from sandy tropical coastline vegetation (*restinga*), as well as the possibility of testing the behavior of other plants, taking into account the associations and symbioses that could become established in the project, in a clear desire to continue the ecological approach used in Minas Gerais.

Various species were introduced for the first time in a Brazilian urban public space, which soon adapted and thrived in the environment, such as *Clusia*

fluminensis Planch. & Triana (abaneiro), *Cecropia lyratiloba* Miq., *Triplaris surinamensis* Cham. (ant-tree), *Ceiba erianthus* (silk-cotton tree), *Bactris setosa* (tucumdo-brejo palm tree). Gradually, the Praça Salgado Filho became a successful test balloon for the more complex project to come: the Parque do Flamengo.

Parque do Flamengo

Carlos Lacerda, the recently inaugurated governor of the state of Guanabara, created after the transfer of the federal capital to Brasília, charged Maria Carlota de Macedo Soares (Lota) with continuing a project that had dragged on through various city governments, namely the conclusion of the urbanization of the reclaimed land along the shoreline of the neighborhoods of Glória and Flamengo. Lota accepted the challenge, although with conditions. She was not in agreement with the original use previous administrations had planned for this unique area reclaimed at such cost from the sea: namely express traffic lanes to solve the problem of communication between the north and south zones of the city. Her plan differed greatly: to create a gigantic park that would preserve some of the city's most singular landscapes, at the same time furnishing improved leisure space for its inhabitants.

To carry the project forward, Lota brought together some of the most respected professionals of the time. Toward the end of 1961, she formed the Work Group for the Urbanization of the Landfill with Affonso Eduardo Reidy, Jorge Machado Moreira, Roberto Burle Marx, Luiz Emygdio de Mello Filho, Hélio Mamede, Sérgio Bernardes and Berta Leitchic. Reidy was charged with the general coordination of the team and the conception and development of the necessary buildings and equipment, together with Moreira, Mamede, Bernardes and Leitchic; Burle Marx was made responsible for the landscaping, assisted by Mello Filho and Maria Augusta Costa Ribeiro.

In February 1962, the group presented the governor with a preliminary study for the park. The occupation of the reclaimed area of around 120 hectares was based on the premise of not creating focuses of interest, but rather implementing the groups of plants and various equipment and buildings along the whole extent of shoreline. There were to be restaurants, sports courts, playgrounds, an area for flying model airplanes, a theater, an aquarium, a bicycle path and a network of paved walkways, in addition to the redevelopment of the beaches for bathing. Pedestrian access would be by overhead walkways and subterranean passages, circumventing the problems posed by the expressway; there would be various parking lots for access by automobile.

The landscaping project was the most complex and ambitious part of the intervention. Dividing the

park into 11 sectors, Burle Marx aimed to formalize the green spaces through the use of a vast selection of shrubs, trees and palms, - 240 species from Brazil and the tropics in general -, making for an experiment unprecedented in his career. The trees and palms were planted in homogenous groups, following landscaping and botanical criteria. Except for the grass areas, there were to be no herbaceous plants in general defining the horizontal planes and volumes of low stature.

The feasibility of realizing a project of this size over a relatively short period naturally presupposes the organization of various simultaneous work fronts. What fled control, however, was the difficulty in harmonizing the objectives and idiosyncrasies at play within these fronts. The method of proceeding with the landfill was one of the first impasses, in 1962. Several of the engineers in charge of the landfill proved adamant in refusing the request of the landscape architect and his assistants to not bury the best soil, leaving only sand on top.

Getting vegetation in sufficient quantity and variety to plant an area of over 1 million square meters had to be planned as if on a war footing, such was the amount of employees and effort involved. First, a nursery for seedlings was set up on a one-hectare site on the landfill itself. This was located on purpose facing the entrance to the bay, so that the behavior of the plants and their adaptation to the environment's salinity and high winds could be tested before their transfer to a permanent site. Nothing previously done was able to serve as an example.

The nursery was supplied with samples collected from the natural environments surrounding the city, furnished by the city's department of parks and gardens and by the Botanical Gardens of Rio de Janeiro, and also taken from the Parque Laje (abandoned at the time) and from old country estates, as well as being brought from outside the state and even the country. Many seedlings were bought from horticulturists and nursery owners in São Paulo and brought to Rio by truck. Seeds were ordered from abroad.

The vast area of the park was planted between 1963 and 1965, requiring around 16,250 samples selected from 240 different species. For many of them, it was their first appearance in Brazilian urban landscaping. This was so with the trees: *Acacia seyal* (pique-de-gazela), *Bauhinia blakeana* (pata-de-vaca), *Bombax malabaricum* (imbirí), *Bumelia obtusifolia* (Ibiranira bumelia), *Calophyllum inophyllum* (apricot), *Chorisia insignis* (a type of silk-cotton tree), *Coccoloba uvifera* (beach berry tree), *Cordia myxa*, *Cordia superba* (a shrub of the Boraginaceae family), *Dillenia indica* (árvore-da-pataca), *Enterolobium contortisiliquum* (tamboril), *Erythrina fluminensis* (coral tree), *Erythrina* sp. (coral tree), *Erythrina velutina* (coral tree), *Ficus*

Fig. 1 – Madalena Cactarium (Praça Euclides da Cunha), 1935-37, Recife.

clusiaefolia (red fig tree), *Hura crepitans*, *Joannesia principes* (anda-açu), *Parkinsonia aculeata* (Jerusalem thorn), *Peltophorum dubium* (farinha-seca shrub), *Pithecellobium tortum* (jacaré), *Pseudobombax ellipticum*, *Schinus terebinthifolius* (pepper tree), *Vitex megapotamica*, among others. And the palms: *Allagoptera arenaria* (guriri), *Butia capitata* (bitiá-da-serra), *Corypha umbraculifera* (talipot-palm) *Dictyosperma album* (palmeira-furação), *Veitchia joannis*, among others.

Even as the planting of the park progressed, political pressures from real estate developers wanting a piece of the cake did not entirely abate. Seeing this, Lota took precautions. In 1964, she consulted Rodrigo de Mello Franco and made a formal request to the Historic and Artistic Heritage Service for the project to be listed. This was the first case in the history of the conservation of national heritage assets that a landscaping and architectural complex became listed as a protected site before it was even finished. However, Lota did not stop there. Seeking to also guarantee a future free of political injunctions and intrigue for the park, in 1965 she set up a foundation charged with its administration, with the backing of various intellectual figures and personalities in the city.

Burle Marx was able to transform an area of landfill that could have easily gone disastrously wrong into one of the most stunningly beautiful locations in the city of Rio de Janeiro. He also created one of the most important symbols of the optimism of a generation that put its faith in its capacity to transform the Brazilian city, making it a better place to live.

Fig. 2 – Parque do Barreiro, 1943-44, Araxá.

Fig. 3 – Parque do Flamengo, 1961-1965, Rio de Janeiro.

KEYWORDS

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